

Design and Characterization of a Free-Beam Laser Microsurgery System based on Rotary Voice Coil Actuators

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INTRODUCTION

Transoral Laser Microsurgery (TLM) is a Minimally Invasive Surgical (MIS) technique for treating diseases in the upper aero-digestive tract. It allows precise tissue resections to better preserve healthy structures and voice quality. Conventional TLM setups rely on joystick-controlled laser micromanipulators, which limit surgical precision, ergonomics, and reproducibility. To address these limitations, robotic devices have been investigated.

Previous research include the work of Giallo et al. [1], who introduced a servo-actuated mechanism but encountered non-linearities and poor reproducibility. Mattos et al. proposed a fast-steering mirror solution [2], while Deshpande et al. employed linear voice-coil motors for direct actuation [3]. However, these approaches faced limitations such as sensitivity to laser alignment and cumbersome designs. Deshpande et al. subsequently proposed a spherical mechanism driven by rotary DC motors and backlash-free gearboxes, which achieved high precision but faced limitations due to high costs and complex implementation [4]. This led to the design of a new laser micromanipulator based on custom rotary voice coil actuators (RVCA), as shown in Fig. 1a. This new design improved previous mechanisms by providing reduced size, reduced mechanical complexity, higher laser steering speed, higher accuracy, and better laser focusing quality [5].

This work advances the RVCA-based micromanipulator by integrating a stylus-based interface, which enables intuitive and ergonomic laser control, and a refined control architecture with adaptive position control loops and feedforward compensation for precise trajectory tracking. Additionally, a model-free compensation approach addresses non-linearities and vibration-induced disturbances, ensuring consistent micrometric precision. Extensive experimentation was conducted to assess the performance of the new device in terms of repeatability, accuracy, control bandwidth, and usability. These experiments and their results are summarized in the following sections.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

System Design

The Computer-Assisted Laser Microsurgery system (CALM) is depicted in Fig. 1, which shows both the RVCA-based laser micromanipulator mechanism and the surgical setup. The control interface of CALM consists

Fig. 1: The CALM system. A) CAD model highlighting the novel mechanism and its laser steering principle. B) Surgical setup including the stylus for device control, an exoscope, and the surgical laser.

of a tablet and a stylus. This interface allows real-time laser steering control and the definition of trajectories for automatic execution by the system. The surgical setup also includes an imaging system (e.g. a microscope or exoscope), and the surgical laser source.

CALM's mechanism governs the roll and pitch motions of a beam-deflecting mirror, redirecting the laser to the desired position. The mechanism consists of two orthogonal RVCA's arranged in a direct-drive configuration. These actuators, composed of lightweight coil and magnet assemblies, offer high torque efficiency, zero backlash, and low inertia. The roll axis features an RVCA integrated with a large ball bearing, ensuring smooth rotation and unobstructed laser transmission, while the pitch axis incorporates a curved RVCA mounted orthogonally, enabling decoupled motion for precise laser positioning.

The stylus is CALM's control device. It integrates a 2 DoF optical position sensor with a resolution of $3.8 \mu\text{m}$, which generates displacement commands for laser steering. These are transmitted to a microcontroller unit, where control routines are implemented to make the laser spot follow the motions of the stylus in real-time. Adjustable motion scaling ensures the system can adapt to a variety of surgical scenarios, enabling the user to execute fine micro-motions or large laser displacements with the necessary precision and speed.

Laser trajectories can be recorded by pressing a button on the stylus, prompting the system to log the laser position at each control loop cycle. Once recorded, trajectories are automatically processed using a spline-based interpolation algorithm, generating waypoints for automatic control. Trajectories are executed in a continuous loop until a new motion command is issued by the stylus. The control loops include fault detection and monitoring features, which

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contribute to enhance the device's safety.

Control Strategy

An adaptive PID control strategy is used to ensure smooth and precise laser steering under dynamic conditions. This accounts for system nonlinearities and contributes to overcome challenges such as Coulomb friction, stiction, and input-output asymmetry. It also ensures precise control near stagnation regions while preventing overshoot during large displacements. Moreover, feedforward compensation is integrated into the control loop to preemptively counteract expected disturbances, ensuring rapid and seamless trajectory tracking. By combining these advanced control strategies with precise actuation, the system achieves micrometric accuracy and robust performance.

Experiments

All experiments described in this paper were performed on a flat target surface located 400mm away from the laser micromanipulator. This is the typical operating distance in TLM. The goal was to assess the performance of CALM, so the experiments included the characterization of its dynamic response through step responses, repeatability according to ISO 230-2, and accuracy based on the execution of circular and 8-shaped trajectories. Both trajectories had a maximum amplitude of 5mm and were executed with speeds varying from 5 to 50mm/s. Furthermore, user trials were conducted to investigate the usability of the device based on the user experience questionnaire (UEQ). For this, they were asked to control the laser to follow 4 different 5mm trajectories while looking at real-time video from the target area.

RESULTS

Dynamic Response: The system exhibited rapid response times, with a range of 1–10 ms for step commands in the range of 1–10mm. Settling times were measured between 7–20 ms, with overshoot remaining below 1% even during the large 10mm displacements. Bandwidth tests revealed cutoff frequencies of 16.67 Hz for roll and 19.85 Hz for pitch when considering 10mm displacements. For the small 1mm displacements, the bandwidth extended to 50 Hz, underscoring the system's ability to respond quickly to motion commands.

Repeatability: The experiment evaluated the system's ability to consistently reach target positions from opposite directions. The maximum bidirectional repeatability (2σ) across the workspace was 81.25 μm , indicating that repeated positions fall within this radius with 95% confidence.

Accuracy: This was measured as the root mean square error (RMSE) over the trajectory during a period of 50 s. The results show an overall RMSE of approximately 80 μm and an average standard deviation of around 50 μm , computed as the mean of standard deviations across all trajectory tested (Fig. 2). This level of accuracy is particularly relevant when compared to the typical laser spot diameter used in surgical procedures, which ranges from 200 μm to 250 μm . With an RMSE well below this range, the system demonstrates sufficient precision to ensure tissue-selective ablation while

Fig. 2: Total RMSE with standard deviation for circular and figure-eight trajectories at different velocities. Data was recorded at 25 Hz for 50 s.

minimizing collateral damage, thereby meeting key clinical requirements for transoral laser microsurgery.

DISCUSSION

This study introduced a new RVCA-based micromanipulator for TLM, demonstrating its capabilities in handling dynamic and complex laser trajectories. Compared to the state-of-the-art, CALM demonstrated significant improvements in terms of size, mechanical complexity, and laser steering performance, achieving a large workspace ($\approx 170 \times 280 \text{mm}^2$), high precision and repeatability (max. error 200 μm , mean error 40 μm), and fast response times.

The integration of an ergonomic stylus-based control interface, an adaptive control strategy, and the possibility to easily record laser trajectories resulted in a system with high usability, which enables users to steer the surgical laser beam with high accuracy and confidence. These characteristics make CALM a promising tool for delicate TLM procedures.

Future work will focus on validating the system performance and usability through end-user trials using ex-vivo tissue (e.g., pig larynxes). Subsequently, engineering refinements will produce a clinical-grade system, which shall be tested through cadaver trials to collect evidence in support of the first in-human trials of CALM. Therefore, the RVCA-based laser micromanipulator presented in this paper represents a strong foundation for advancing transoral microsurgery technology and improving surgical outcomes.

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